

UAV LiDAR and GNSS Surveys for High-Accuracy Spatial Data Acquisition Case Studies from Croatia and Bosnia and Herzegovina

Nikola Kranjčić ^{a,*}, Vlado Cetl ^a, Hrvoje Matijević ^a, Danko Markovinović ^a

^a University North, Department of Geodesy and Geomatics, nkranjcic@unin.hr ; vcetl@unin.hr ; hmatijevic@unin.hr ; danko.markovinovic@unin.hr

* Nikola Kranjčić, nkranjcic@unin.hr

Keywords: UAV LiDAR, GNSS RTK/PPK, Coordinate Reference System, CROPOS, FBiHPOS, DEM/DSM, Spatial Data Infrastructure

Abstract:

The acquisition of high-accuracy spatial data is essential for geodesy, civil engineering, cadastre, and environmental monitoring. This paper presents the integration of UAV-based LiDAR mapping and GNSS RTK/PPK positioning as a methodological framework for ensuring centimeter-level precision in national and regional spatial data infrastructures.

Surveys were performed in Croatia (Donja Višnjica, Gornje Jesenje, Jakopovec, Kapelščak, Laz Bistrički, Strmec) using the CROPOS GNSS network within the official HTRS96/TM coordinate system, and in Bosnia and Herzegovina (Jezerac well, Goranci – Mostar) using the FBiHPOS network within the official MGI 1901 / Balkans zone 6 system. These dual frameworks emphasize both the opportunities and challenges of cross-border geospatial interoperability (Idrizi et al., 2018).

A DJI Matrice 350 RTK UAV equipped with a DJI Zenmuse L2 LiDAR sensor and supported by an Emlid Reach RS2 GNSS receiver enabled surveys with centimeter-level accuracy (RMSE: X = 0.006 m; Y = 0.005 m; Z = 0.007 m). Data were processed in DJI Terra and Lidar360, producing dense point clouds (>240 pts/m²), high-resolution orthophotos (~2–3 cm GSD), and DEM/DSM products.

Results highlight that UAV-LiDAR surveys integrated with national GNSS infrastructures not only ensure compatibility with CROPOS and FBiHPOS, but also strengthen interoperability with European systems such as ETRS89 (Idrizi, 2021). This contributes to sustainable, harmonized spatial data infrastructures supporting scientific research, engineering applications, and long-term monitoring. Results are seen in Table 1, and a comparison of DEM and DSM generated from UAV-LiDAR surveys is seen in Figure 1.

Table 1. Summary of UAV-LiDAR Survey Parameters

Parameter	Dataset	Resolution/scale
UAV platform	DJI Matrice 350 RTK	DJI Matrice 350 RTK
LiDAR sensor	DJI Zenmuse L2	DJI Zenmuse L2
GNSS corrections	CROPOS (RTK/PPK)	FBiHPOS (RTK)
Coordinate system	HTRS96/TM (EPSG:3765)	MGI 1901 / Balkans zone 6 (Gauss-Krüger) (EPSG:3908 or EPSG:8678)
Point cloud density	~240 pts/m ²	~247 pts/m ²
Horizontal accuracy (RMSE)	0.007 m	0.006 m
Vertical accuracy (RMSE)	0.014 m	0.007 m

Figure 1. Comparison of DEM (left) and DSM (right) generated from UAV-LiDAR survey

References

- Idrizi, B., Pashova, L., Kabashi, I., Mulic, M., Krdzalic, D., Tutic, D., Vucetic, N., Kevic, K., Nikolic, G., & Djurovic, R. (2018). Study of length differences from topography to map projection within the state coordinate systems for some countries on the Balkan Peninsula. In Proceedings of the FIG Congress 2018. https://www.fig.net/resources/proceedings/fig_proceedings/fig2018/papers/ts08e/TS08E_idrizi_pashova_et_a_l_9602.pdf
- Idrizi, B. (2021). Redefining of “EPSG” and “PROJ” for current State Coordinate Reference System of the Republic of North Macedonia. *Proceedings of the International Cartographic Association*, 4, 45. <https://doi.org/10.5194/ica-proc-4-45-2021>